

The Effectiveness of Sorghum Seed Content as a Skin Care Cosmetic

I Gusti Agung Istri Mas Dianti Pratiwi, Cok Istri Sitananda Amrita, Padma Vimala

Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Warmadewa University, Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia

Correspondence: diantigm@gmail.com

Abstract

Agriculture is one of the goals in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Sustainable agriculture requires an innovation that can boost processed agricultural products, one form of innovation is in the field of cosmetics. One of the utilizations can use the content of sorghum, namely through sorghum extract and oil which contains bioactive compounds such as polyphenols and antioxidants, which can be useful in skin and hair care. Based on this, researchers want to make a breakthrough innovation in skin care products in the form of balm stick preparations with antioxidant content, and polyphenols which are beneficial in increasing collagen and elastin production. Briefly, sorghum seed extract was macerated with 96% ethanol for 2x24 hours then GCMS analysis test was carried out on the extract that had been obtained. Stikbalm preparation was carried out by melting petroleum gel using the double-boiler technique with a formulation of 100:75:50. An organoleptic test was carried out on the stick balm preparation, then the stick balm was applied to mice that had been injured and then observed every stage of wound healing. Our finding showed that obtained stick balm with 100% formulation has the best results for wound healing.

Keywords: balm stick, sorghum, stretch mark

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is one of the key goals in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The ministry's focus in agriculture is to promote sustainable agriculture. Sustainable agriculture requires innovations that can enhance agricultural products, one of which is in the field of cosmetics. One potential application is the use of sorghum extracts and oil. Sorghum contains bioactive compounds such as polyphenols and antioxidants, which can be beneficial for skin and hair care.

Sorghum contains phenolic and flavonoid compounds, such as quercetin and kaempferol, which can help boost collagen and elastin production in the skin. Sorghum extract also has antioxidant effects that help protect the skin from damage caused by sun exposure and free radicals (Ndlovu, 2018).

Based on this, researchers aim to create a breakthrough innovation in the form of a balm stick skincare product. This product is expected not only to act as a skincare agent but also to prevent

inflammation and accelerate wound healing. The specific aim is to observe the wound healing process until it leaves no visible scars, often referred to as stretch marks. This needs to be studied to assess the benefits provided by the balm stick made from sorghum seeds (Harnanti, 2019).

In the recovery process of stretch marks, the increased synthesis of collagen helps repair damage and improve skin elasticity (Luebberding et al., 2015). Adequate skin moisturization is essential in skincare, particularly in the recovery of stretch marks. Well-hydrated skin has better elasticity and is more capable of reducing the appearance of wrinkles and skin imperfections (Makrantonaki et al., 2012).

METHODS

The research process includes proposal preparation, ethical feasibility testing, sorghum seed extract production, GC-MS analysis, balm stick formulation, organoleptic testing, animal model preparation, balm stick application, and wound healing tests.

The extraction method used to obtain sorghum seed extract involves 96% ethanol

as a solvent. The process involves a 1:5 ratio between sorghum seeds and the solvent, where the mixture is soaked for two 24-hour periods. Afterward, the mixture is filtered, and the filtrate is placed into a rotary evaporator. The resulting extract can be further processed as needed, including adjusting concentration variations (Azzahra & Hayati, 2018).

In this study, the chemical composition of the product and the identification of its components were analyzed using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) (Mladenović et al., 2023).

The extraction process was carried out using the maceration method, where the powder was dispersed in 75% ethanol. Maceration was conducted for three days, followed by concentration using a water bath at 60°C. The balm stick formulation began by melting petroleum jelly using a double boiler technique. Once the petroleum jelly melted, sorghum seed extract was added to the mixture and stirred until evenly combined. The liquid mixture was then poured into balm stick containers and left to cool and harden. Once the balm stick had completely cooled and solidified, the container was sealed.

Next, an organoleptic test was conducted to evaluate the physical, chemical, and organoleptic properties of the product, such as color, odor, texture, and skin absorption ability (Maulidiani, 2020).

Before applying the balm stick, the test animals, or mice, were acclimatized for seven days and provided with adequate food and water to eliminate other influencing factors. Afterward, the mice's backs were shaved. A subcutaneous injection of lidocaine at a dose of 0.1 cc/100 g was administered before inducing a wound approximately 2 cm in diameter on the shaved area (Fazri, 2019).

The application of the balm stick began by cleaning the area to be treated, following the guidelines from the Ministry of Health. The wound was cleaned with an alcohol swab to maintain sterility, after which the balm stick was applied. The application was done every 24 hours (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022; Zubaydah & Sahumena, 2021).

The wounds were observed using several methods, starting with a visual evaluation of wound closure. This was done by measuring the diameter of the wound and calculating its area using the formula for the area of a circle. The collected data were analyzed using statistical methods. The second method involved measuring the wound healing time, which was evaluated from the moment the wound began to close until the healing process was complete (Fazri, 2019; Nasution & Yenita, 2020; Sari et al., 2019).

RESULTS

GC/MS Analysis Results

The analysis results show that nine peaks were successfully extracted from ethanol solvent with different Similarity Index (SI) values (Table 1). Gas chromatography and mass spectrometry revealed the presence of linalool, acetic acid, linalyl acetate, hexadecanoic acid, eicosane, oxybenzone, and beta pregnane, which are known to have positive effects on stretch marks. The most abundant compound in the sorghum extract is found in peak 8, with an area percentage of 17.03, possibly identified as oxybenzone.

Tabel 1. GC/MS

RT	Area %	Library	Quality	Function	Structure
5.076	14.52	LINALOOL	97	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant.	 (C ₁₀ H ₁₈ O)

5.65 7	10.6 7	Acetic acid	98	pH skin balance, antimicrobial, and antifungal.	 (C₂H₄O₂)
5.71 9	5.84	3,5,5-Trimethylhexyl acetate	90	as aromatherapy	 (C₁₁H₂₂O₂)
6.36 7	12.0 5	Linalyl acetate	91	Anti-inflammatory, Antimicrobial	 (C₁₂H₂₀O₂)
8.28 6	10.6 0	Phenol	98	Antiseptic	 (C₆H₆O)
14.4 10	12.4 9	Hexadecanoic acid	98	Natural moisturizer, skin protection from UV rays and free radicals, anti-inflammatory, and can enhance the absorption of active ingredients in skincare products.	 (C₁₆H₃₂O₂)
15.5 46	12.4 4	Eicosane	91	Forms a skin barrier, moisturizes the skin, softens the skin, enhances the absorption of skincare ingredients, and improves the stability of skincare products.	 (C₂₀H₄₂)
15.8 41	17.0 3	Oxybenzone	95	UV B Protection	 (C₁₄H₁₂O₃)

16.4 30	4.37	BETA PREGNAN E	99	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, prevents oxidative stress on the skin, accelerates wound healing, speeds up collagen formation, promotes scar tissue formation.	 (C₂₅H₃₁NO₆)
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STIK BALM FORMULATION

The research began by sterilizing glass and metal materials using an autoclave, as well as preparing other supporting materials. The extraction process was carried out using the maceration method. The sorghum seed powder was dispersed in 75% ethanol, and maceration was performed for three days, followed by concentration using a water bath at a temperature of 60°C.

The balm stick formulation started by melting petroleum jelly using a double boiler technique. Once the petroleum jelly melted, sorghum seed extract was added to the mixture and stirred until well combined. The liquid mixture was then poured into balm stick containers and left to cool and solidify.

ORGANOLEPTIC TEST RESULT

Based on the organoleptic test results in Table 2, the first formulation, which consists of 100% sorghum seed extract mixed with petroleum jelly, received the highest scores on every item. This indicates that the sorghum stretch mark eraser formulation 1 that we produced has achieved good physical results.

Tabel 2. Uji Organoleptik.

Pomade	Smell (%)		Texture (%)		Hot (%)		Rough (%)		Dry (%)		Smooth (%)	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Sorghum stretch mark eraser	100	0	96,67	3,33	0	100	0	100	0	100	100	0
Obat luar komersial	90	10	88,33	11,67	0	100	0	100	0	100	100	0
Gentamisin	95	5	91,67	8,33	0	100	0	100	0	100	100	0

BURN WOUND HEALING TEST RESULT

Based on the results of the burn wound healing test, it was found that wounds treated with the sorghum stretch mark eraser formulation 1 showed faster and better healing compared to wounds treated with betadine sorghum. The final wound healing results from the application of the sorghum stretch mark eraser were similar to the final healing results from the application of gentamicin as therapy.

CONCLUSION

Formulation 1, with a composition of 100% sorghum seed extract mixed with petroleum jelly, has the potential to brighten the skin, tighten the skin, stimulate collagen production, and fade or even eliminate stretch marks. Additionally, this product possesses anti-inflammatory properties that can soothe skin inflammation, as well as antioxidant properties that protect the skin from damage caused by free radicals.

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